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*Asia Khilkovska***NEW PARADIGM OF BUSINESS
COMMUNICATION**

The author addresses the need to update and modernize the content of the discipline *Business English*, an essential component of many Higher education programmes. The paper examines the advantages of *Market Leader*, a course widely used in Ukrainian universities, whose structure and materials kept it relevant for many years. The author argues for supplementing the course with a broad range of up to date English language sources—from leading economic publications (*The Economist*, *Financial Times*, *Harvard Business Review*) to contemporary educational platforms for entrepreneurs and start ups (startup.info, Pleadry Blog, etc.). Being used in class, these resources ensure continuous alignment with the dynamics of the modern business environment, where new entrepreneurial models, development trends, and communication practices are formed.

The analysis of recent methodological publications highlights the areas of the discipline that require content renewal in order to equip learners with communication skills relevant to today's rapidly evolving business context. Scholarly literature emphasizes the importance of focusing on practical professional competencies, including models such as the 4Cs (communication, collaboration, critical thinking, creativity). Researchers also underscore the role of Business English as a Lingua Franca, which necessitates the development of linguacultural competencies. Additional priorities include building skills in digital communication tools, mastering new models of corporate interaction, and acquiring contemporary business terminology that reflects global market trends. However, the author argues that it is equally important to draw learners' attention to significant shifts in modern business philosophy, which directly influence language use and communication models. These shifts include the movement from a "profit above all" paradigm toward values such as ethics, trust, transparency, social responsibility, sustainability, and inclusivity; the transition "from hierarchy to a team," which transforms interaction within organizations and among stakeholders; and the shift "from technocratic to philosophical and reflective thinking."

Engagement with current sources provides learners not only with access to the latest business practices but also with understanding of contemporary business philosophy, which is crucial, as effective business communication relies

on the ability to articulate one's own values clearly and to understand the values of others—skills that underpin the success of both entrepreneurs and employees.

Key words: business communication, values, ethics, trust, transparency.

Хільковська Ася Олександрівна. Нова парадигма бізнес-комунікації.

Автор торкається теми оновлення та осучаснення змісту дисципліни Business English (Ділова англійська або Бізнес Англійська), яка є невід'ємною складовою багатьох освітніх програм вищої школи. В роботі розглядаються переваги популярного в українських вишах курсу Market Leader, що використовується при вивченні дисципліни і характеристики якого дозволяють йому залишатися актуальним протягом багатьох років.

Автор аргументує необхідність доповнення курсу широким спектром актуальних англомовних джерел – від провідних економічних видань (*The Economist, Financial Times, Harvard Business Review*) до сучасних освітніх платформ для підприємців і стартапів (startup.info, Pleadly Blog тощо), що забезпечує постійний зв'язок із динамікою сучасного бізнес-середовища, де формуються нові моделі підприємництва, тенденції розвитку та комунікативні практики. Проведений аналіз методичних публікацій останніх років визначає зони дисципліни, що потребують оновлення змісту, щоб забезпечити здобувачам освіти релевантні комунікативні навички для динамічного бізнес-середовища. Наукова література наголошує на необхідності орієнтації на практичні професійні компетентності, зокрема пропонує моделі на кшталт 4С (комунікація, колаборація, критичне мислення, креативність). Дослідники також підкреслюють роль бізнес-англійської як Lingua Franca, що зумовлює важливість формування лінгвокультурних компетентностей. Додатковими пріоритетами є розвиток умінь працювати з цифровими інструментами комунікації, опанування нових моделей корпоративної взаємодії та засвоєння актуальної бізнес-термінології, яка відображає сучасні тенденції глобального ринку. Але на думку автора, не менш важливим є звернути увагу здобувачів освіти на суттєві зміни в сучасній філософії бізнесу, що безпосередньо впливають на мову та моделі комунікації: зсув від парадигми «прибуток понад усе» до цінностей етики, довіри, прозорості, соціальної відповідальності, сталості та інклюзивності, перехід «від ієрархії до команди», що змінює характер взаємодії всередині організацій і між стейкхолдерами, рух «від технократичного до філософського та рефлексивного мислення».

Ознайомлення з актуальними джерелами дає здобувачам освіти не лише доступ до новітніх бізнес-практик, а й розуміння сучасної філософії бізнесу.

Це критично важливо, адже ефективне бізнес-спілкування ґрунтується на вмінні чітко комунікувати власні цінності та розуміти цінності інших – навичках, що визначають успіх як підприємців, так і найманих фахівців.

Ключові слова: бізнес-комунікація, цінності, етика, довіра, прозорість.

Since the establishment of the Foreign Languages Department for non philology specialties in 1993, shortly after the People's Ukrainian Academy was founded, the chosen strategy has been to teach English as a tool for professional communication. As a result, learners were expected to discuss professional topics, solve real life problems, and role play workplace situations at any level of language proficiency, starting from the elementary level. This in class communication approach prioritized tasks, message, and meaning over accuracy, encouraging students to use the target language for a variety of communicative purposes. In searching for a course that would best meet the professional needs of Business and Management students at all levels of language proficiency, the teaching staff chose the popular Pearson edition *Market Leader*. *Market Leader* is widely considered a strong choice for Business English because it combines authentic business content, practical communication skills, and structured language development in a way that aligns closely with real workplace needs, therefore Ukrainian universities often choose it (now its third edition) as a main course book.

The strengths of the course are well known to both teachers and students. It was developed and has been regularly updated in collaboration with the Financial Times, which provides access to up to date authentic articles, interviews, and expert opinions on business issues. Each edition places strong emphasis on functional language, and every unit includes lessons aimed at developing specific business skills—such as presenting, negotiating, writing correspondence, and conducting meetings—as well as sections devoted to intercultural aspects of doing business. An important part of the *Market Leader* course is its case studies, which conclude every unit and allow students to test their language competences and soft skills by communicating effectively, making decisions, and solving real life problems that may arise in an English speaking professional environment. This approach—teaching communication through communication while

working toward goals beyond language itself (task based learning, TBL, or problem based learning, PBL)—is widely recognized as effective in contemporary teaching methodology [5]. *Market Leader* is structured according to the five CEFR levels (A1 to C1), and even A1 students take part in case studies. The knowledge they acquire while working through each unit is then applied to group problem solving tasks conducted in English.

Although *Market Leader* remains a high quality and up to date course, there is a unanimous view among teachers and methodologists that Business English is a subject whose content requires constant, day to day updating. Without such updating, universities cannot be sure they are equipping learners with communication skills relevant to the contemporary business environment. Among the improvements suggested in recent research is a new course structure based on required professional competences rather than communication topics or grammar structures [2]. Different authors propose their own sets of competences, such as the 4Cs: communication, collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity. [1]. Some researchers emphasize the role of Business English as a Lingua Franca (BELF) in the context of globalized business. They argue that the subject should primarily focus on developing linguo cultural competences [3]. The research also highlights the relevance of digital communication tools and the growing market demand for related skills, as well as the emergence of new models of corporate communication [4]. There is also a broad consensus among educators and researchers that new business concepts and recently developed terminology should be incorporated into Business English courses and classroom practice.

We can also identify an area that, in our view, does not receive the attention it deserves: a significant shift in business philosophy which determines its language and communication styles and which has taken place over the past couple of decades. Recent publications indicate a clear shift from a “profit above all” philosophy toward the principles of ethics, trust, and responsibility. Companies increasingly strive to act ethically, to build trust through honesty and transparency, and to demonstrate social responsibility. There is also a growing public demand for sustainability, accountability, and inclusion, which encourages businesses to communicate and promote their values more explicitly.

We can also observe that more and more companies are adopting innovative and flexible management models. This shift can be described as a movement “from hierarchy to team.” It has a profound impact on both internal and external communication. While hierarchical companies operate like clockwork, modern businesses function more like communities, which in turn form larger networks that include a wide range of stakeholders.

Another transition in business and entrepreneurship that deserves attention in the context of a business language classroom is the shift from technocratic thinking to a more philosophical and reflective one. Companies are increasingly seeking philosophical approaches to problem solving and decision making, to leadership and team building, to innovation and creative thinking, and to ethics and understanding human behaviour—whether in customers or employees. The new business philosophy has enriched business communication with new terminology—such as trust, transparency, social responsibility, accountability, empathy, inclusion, agile, and data driven—which originally stems from the fields of ethics, philosophy, and psychology, and has acquired new dimensions in the business context. Some of this terminology has found its place not only in professional literature but also in course books such as *Market Leader*—for example, sustainability, ethical business, and company mission. Other concepts, however, have remained outside the attention of course writers. For instance, the terms “crisis communication” or “personal brand” are not mentioned even once in the course.

Bringing authentic materials into a Business English classroom, alongside conventional course books, is essential for learning the language of business communication. It is authentic business sources that expose students to current business practices and contemporary business philosophy. This is particularly important, as modern business communication is grounded in expressing one’s own values and understanding the values of others, and this type of communication—when effective—forms the basis of business success for both employers and employees.

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